

TO THE QUESTION LOGISTICS SYSTEMS

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Annotation.

the article contains the basis of the logistics system and the definition of logistics, as well as the class of tasks to be solved. The analysis of solved and logistical problems, the management of material and information flows with them, dedicated to transport and industrial logistics, the class of the problem is given as a minimum problem.

Key words.

logistics, logistics systems, transport logistics, production logistics, warehouse logistics, material, information flow of the algorithm.

Logistics is a set of tasks related to the management of material and related to the management of material and information flows with them. Before defining logistics, let's visualize the process of material flow management.

As a physical example, let's take a stream of water flowing from a faucet. You can control this flow using various actions - closing or opening a tap, adding hot or cold water. You can turn the mixer tap to the shower, or you can use a flexible hose to direct the flow of water in any direction [1].

As a result of these actions, the intensity of the flow, its direction change; the qualitative characteristic changes - the temperature, when the jet is sprayed through the shower net, the structure changes despite the diverse material flow circulating in economic systems, their control is in principle similar to the control of a water jet:

"opened the tap" more - increased supplies:

"closed the tap" - stopped the supply.

You can change the addressee - the flow will take a different path, you can change the qualitative composition of the flow, change the range of goods supplied, etc.

Despite a certain similarity of the considered objects, the management of material flows in economic systems is much more complicated. Here, in addition to

direct operations with material flows (loading, unloading, transportation, etc.), it includes:

- 1) Various commercial transactions, as a result of which there is an agreement between the parties on the flow of flows and their parameters;
- 2) Search for rational forms. Forwarding services for cargo recipients;
- 3) Determining the optimal paths for material flows to go, as well as places where they will be temporarily accumulated, as well as many other types of work.

Material flow management, like any other object, consists of two parts:

- 1) Decision making.
- 2) Implementation of the decision.

In order to make informed decisions on the management of material flows, certain knowledge is required. This knowledge relates to logistics;

Accordingly, a large group defines logistics as a science or scientific direction:

Logistics is an interdisciplinary scientific direction, directly related to the search for new opportunities to improve the efficiency of material flows [2].

How the science of logistics sets and solves the following tasks [2].

- 1) Demand forecast and inventory planning;
- 2) Determining the required capacity of production and transport;
- 3) Development of scientific management of finished products based on the optimal management of material flows;
- 4) Development of scientific foundations for managing transshipment processes and transport and storage operations at production points and at consumers;
- 5) Construction of various variants of mathematical models of the functioning of logical systems;
- 6) Development of methods for joint planning, marketing and shipment of finished products and other tasks.

The knowledge developed by science makes it possible to justify decisions in the field of material flow management.

For the practical implementation of the decisions taken, concrete actions are needed. Therefore, another group of definitions considers logistics as an economic activity: Logistics is a direction of economic activity, which consists in managing material flows in the areas of production and circulation.

We present the principal sphere of end-to-end material flow - the main object of logistics, starting from the primary source of raw materials in the raft to the final consumer [3]. Fig 1.

Figure. 1. Principal sphere of through material flow.

It is obvious that the composition of the flow changes as you move along the chain, at first between the source of raw materials and the first processing enterprise, as well as between different industries, as a rule, massive homogeneous goods move, and at the end of the material flow chain is represented by a variety of ready-to-consume goods. Within individual industries, material flows also take place. Here, between the shops or inside the shops, various parts, blanks, semi-finished products are mixed. During the logistics process, the material flow is delivered to the enterprise, then its rational promotion is organized through warehouse and production areas, after which the finished product is brought to the consumer in accordance with the order after this [4].

Analyzing the scientific and practical work of logistics [5, 6, 7, 8] from the point of view of managing the movement of material flows, as well as automated systems for managing the movement of material flows, it turned out that logistics systems differ from each other in structure, enterprise size, functions, warehouse economy, their development strategy and other elements. Logistic systems have significant quality, quantity of function links and are influenced by environmental factors. As logistics systems, one can consider an industrial enterprise, a trading enterprise, the infrastructure of the economy of a country or a group of countries.

The main goal of the logistics system is to deliver goods, in the right quantity and assortment, and as far as possible ready for production or personal consumption, to the place required by consumers (the right product at the right time and right place) at a given level of logistics costs.

The elements of the links are enterprises - suppliers of material resources, manufacturing enterprises and their divisions, marketing, intermediary organizations, transport and forwarding enterprises, exchanges, banks, information

and computer service enterprises. Most of the links of the logistics system is a synthesis of subjects and objects of management with their own criteria for optimizing the functioning, which greatly complicates the management of the logistics system.

Logistics systems are divided into groups: micrologistics systems and macrologistics systems. Micrologistics systems - industrial, commercial enterprises and others - are designed to manage and optimize material information, financial flows in the production or supply process and solve the problems of efficient use of material resources, accelerating the working capital of an enterprise, reducing main production time, inventory management in a warehouse system for optimizing work technological transport.

The problem to be solved by micrologistic systems is the rational organization and preservation of the movement of material resources and finished products, reducing the time for fulfilling consumer orders.

Here is the structure of the micrologistic system Fig. 2

RMF	RMF	-	RMF	-	RMF
- Purchases		Production	procedure	Management of order	
-Transportation		management		procedures	
-Inventory		- Intra-factory		- Transportation	
Management		transportation		Protective packaging	
- Warehousing		- Inventory		- Cargo handling	
- Cargo handling		Management		- Warehousing	
-Collection	of	- Maintaining quality		- Inventory	
returnable waste, containers		standards for the production		Management	
		FP		- Provision of spare	
		- Protective packaging		parts and service	
		- Cargo handling		- Support for the return	
		- Warehousing		FP of the collection of	
		- Pricing		returnable waste, containers	

		- Support for customer service standards - Pricing
Logistics operations (functions)		
Information and computer support		

Fig.2. The structure of the micrologistics system

⇔ - material flows, → - information and financial flows; MR - material resources; FP - finished products; RMF - return material flows

Logistics solves local problems within individual links, provides logical operations for planning, implementing and controlling the processes of moving goods inside or outside industrial enterprises [9].

The macrologistic system solves problems in relation to the infrastructure of the economy of an individual country or group of countries.

At each link or node, the logistics system tasks are delivered separately, and so they are as follows:

- a new direction in the organization of the movement of goods;
- the theory of planning various flows in human-machine systems;
- a set of various activities in order to obtain the required amount of cargo in the right place at the right time with minimal cost;
- efficient movement of finished products from the place of production to the place of consumption;
- the science of the rational organization of production and distribution, as well as other tasks.

Studying the scientific practical work of the logistics system, as well as conducting an abstract study: [6, 7, 8, 9, 10] we draw the following conclusions:

- 1) In each link of the logistics system, solving problems, is - the task of the minimum - min.
- 2) In each link of the production logistics system, the task is - the task of the maximum - max.
- 3) Transport logistics - the science of planning, controlling and managing transportation, warehousing and other tangible and non-tangible operations performed in the process of delivering raw materials and materials to a manufacturing enterprise, inside factory processing, raw materials and semi-finished products and delivering finished products to the consumer in accordance with the interests and requirements of the latter, as well as the transfer, storage and processing of relevant information [11, 13, 14, 16].

4) In the theory of logistics, functions and principles are formed on the basis of basic concepts and rules. In each node of the logistics system, the corresponding tasks are defined. These tasks are based on the following rules.

- 1) Cargo - the desired product;
- 2) Quality - the required quality;
- 3) Quantity - in the required quantity;
- 4) Time - at a certain time;
- 5) Location - at minimal cost.

If all the rules are combined, then as a result it is possible to define the concept of "logistics" - the delivery of the prescribed cargo to certain places at the appointed time in the required quantity and appropriate quality at minimal cost.

The main sources studying the theory of logistics distinguish the following areas [17]:

In all directions of the logistics tasks being solved, in each link of the logistics system, fulfilling the following conditions: consumer criteria with minimal costs - task min.

In each link of the logistics system, the material flow will describe the model of transportation from the point of origin to the point of the consumer, transport costs should be minimal [18].

We accept the following interpretation [12].

i - the number of the point of the sender of the material flow.

j - consumer's destination number

A_j - the volume of the sent material of the i - point.

B_j - required volume of material j - consumer

C_{ij} - i - expenditure costs per unit of cargo from the sender's point to the consumer's point.

X_{ij} is the volume of the necessary material transferred from point i to point j of the consumer.

It is necessary to determine the value of X_{ij} so that, this function F must be minimal.

$F = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m C_{ij} X_{ij} \rightarrow \min$ and fulfillment of the following conditions.

1. $\sum_{j=1}^m X_{ij} = A_i \quad (i = 1 \div n)$

The transported volume of material must correspond to the volume of the produced material goods.

2. $\sum_{i=1}^n X_{ij} = B_j \quad (j = 1 \div m)$

The transported material, or cheese, must meet the needs of the consumer.

3. $X_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (i = \overline{1-n}); \quad (j = \overline{1-m})$

These are not negativity conditions. Still, it can be identified as follows.

Find the values of X_{ij} so that as a result the function

$$F = C_{ij}X_{ij} + C_{12}X_{12} + \dots + C_{mn}X_{mn} \rightarrow \min$$

and the following conditions must be met

- 1) $X_{ij} = A_i$
- 2) $X_{ij} = B_j$
- 3) $X_{ij} \geq 0 \quad (i = \overline{1, n}); \quad (j = \overline{1, m})$

The right sides of the equation are equal, so the following is true:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n A_i = \sum_{j=1}^m B_j$$

The solution of this model of material flow transportation in the chain of the logistics system is solved by different methods.

Accordingly, there is a solution algorithm and a computational application package [16, 17, 18, 19].

Solving the problem of the logistics system, formulated by the necessary service and system programs, as well as a package of applied programs, solves problems of a distributive type [12].

The developed algorithm and application software package is a methodological and applied basis for solving the problem of transport logistics [18, 19].

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